

1 Multicomponent Network Formation in Selective 2 Layer of Composite Membrane for CO₂ Separation

3 Jelena Lillepär¹, Evgeni Sperling¹, Marit Blanke^{1,2}, Martin Held¹ and Sergey Shishatskiy¹

4 ¹ Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht, Institute of Polymer Research, Max-Planck-Str. 1, 21502 Geesthacht,
5 Germany; evgeni.sperling@hzg.de (E.S.); martin.held@hzg.de (M.H.); sergey.shishatskiy@hzg.de (S.Sh.)

6 ² Current address: marit.blanke@gmx.de

7 • Correspondence: jelena.lillepaerg@hzg.de; Tel.: +49-4152-87-2448 (J.L.)

8 Supporting Information for the Manuscript

9 **Table S1.** Chemical structure of components used for network formation.

Commercial name	Code	Chain structure	Fragment
PolyActive™	P1500		
Poly(propylene glycol) diglycidyl ether	PPG380 PPG340		n~4.3 n~9
Poly(ethylene glycol) diglycidyl ether	PEG5265		n~9
Trimethylolpropane triglycidyl ether	TPT302		-
Jeffamine® ED-series	JED600 JED900 JED2000		l~9.0; (m+n)~3.6 l~12.5; (m+n)~6.0 l~39; (m+n)~6.0
Jeffamine® T-series			(x+y+z) ~ 5-6
<p>Reaction between amino- and glycidyl-end groups:</p> $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{R}-\text{NH}_2 + \text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{O})-\text{R}'-\text{CH}(\text{O})-\text{CH}_2 \longrightarrow \cdots-\text{R}'-\text{CH}(\text{OH})-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}-\text{R}-\cdots$			

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12 **Figure S1.** Thin film composite membrane structure prepared for this study.

13 **Figure S2.** SEM images of upper surface of P1500 thick films: (a) Pristine film without additives; (b-
 14 f) Films with additives: (b) JED600PPG380; (c) JED600PPG640; (d) JED600TPT302; (e) JT403PPG640;
 15 (f) JT403TPT302.

16 **Table S2.** Thicknesses of TFCM taken from SEM micrographs of the cross section. Standard deviations
 17 for 10 specimens are presented in parentheses.

Top layer of TFCM	Thickness of top layer (nm)
Gutter layer	226 (11)
P1500	214 (45)
P1500 with 30 % JED600TPT302 (Figure 3) ¹	315 (194)
P1500 with 30% JED600PPG640 (Figure 3) ¹	458 (91)

P1500 with 37 % JED600TPT302 (Figure 7) ²	267 (70)
P1500 with 37 % JED600PPG640 (Figure 7) ²	195 (69)

18 ¹ Direct contact with polymers solution. ² Using a subsidiary roll between solution bath and moving support
 19 gives the different in the thickness of coated layer.

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21 **Figure S3.** SEM images of uppers surfaces of P1500 TFCMs: (a) Pristine membrane without additives;
 22 (b-f) Membranes with additives: (b) JED600PPG380; (c) JED600PPG640; (d) JED600TPT302;
 23 (e) JT403PPG640; (f) JT403TPT302.

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Table S3. DSC measurements for selected TFCM with network formation.

Component	T _g (°C)	T _c (°C)	T _m (°C)
P1500	-49	11 ¹	28 ¹
JED600PPG380	-30	5	28
JED600PPG640	-45	12	30
JT403TPT302	-47	5	28
JED600TPT302	-19	6	29
JT403PPG640	-25	10	30

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